

Fuga numero 2

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B $\flat$ Clarinet

Violin

Cello

Detailed description: This system contains three staves. The top staff is for B $\flat$ Clarinet, the middle for Violin, and the bottom for Cello. All three staves are in 3/4 time with a key signature of two sharps (F# and C#). The B $\flat$ Clarinet staff contains a melodic line starting with a quarter rest, followed by eighth and sixteenth notes. The Violin and Cello staves contain whole rests throughout the system.

B $\flat$ Cl.

Vln.

Vc.

Detailed description: This system contains three staves. The top staff is for B $\flat$ Clarinet, the middle for Violin, and the bottom for Cello. All three staves are in 3/4 time with a key signature of two sharps. The B $\flat$ Clarinet staff contains a melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes. The Violin staff contains whole rests. The Cello staff contains a melodic line starting with a quarter rest, followed by eighth and sixteenth notes.

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3 $\flat$ Cl.

Vln.

Vc.

The first system of the musical score consists of three staves. The top staff is for the 3 $\flat$ Clarinet (Cl.), the middle for Violin (Vln.), and the bottom for Violoncello (Vc.). The key signature is two sharps (F# and C#), and the time signature is 3/4. The Cl. part begins with a melodic line of eighth and quarter notes. The Vln. part has a whole rest in the first two measures, followed by a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes. The Vc. part provides a bass line with eighth and quarter notes.

3 $\flat$ Cl.

Vln.

Vc.

The second system continues the musical score with the same three staves. The Cl. part continues its melodic line. The Vln. part features a more active rhythmic pattern with sixteenth and eighth notes. The Vc. part continues with a steady bass line, including some sixteenth-note passages.

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3^b Cl.

Vln.

Vc.

3^b Cl.

Vln.

Vc.

Fuga numero 2

3 $\flat$ Cl.

Vln.

Vc.

The first system of the musical score consists of three staves. The top staff is for the 3 $\flat$ Clarinet (3 $\flat$ Cl.) in treble clef with a key signature of two sharps (F# and C#). It features a melodic line with quarter and eighth notes, including some rests. The middle staff is for the Violin (Vln.) in treble clef, playing a rhythmic accompaniment of eighth notes with some accidentals. The bottom staff is for the Violoncello (Vc.) in bass clef, providing a bass line with eighth notes and rests.

3 $\flat$ Cl.

Vln.

Vc.

The second system of the musical score continues the three parts. The 3 $\flat$ Clarinet part has more complex rhythmic patterns, including sixteenth notes and rests. The Violin part continues its eighth-note accompaniment with various accidentals. The Violoncello part has a more active bass line with eighth notes and rests.

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3^b Cl.

Vln.

Vc.

3^b Cl.

Vln.

Vc.

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Fuga numero 2

3^b Cl.

Vln.

Vc.

This system contains measures 6 through 12 of the piece. The 3^b Cl. part features a melodic line with eighth-note patterns and rests. The Vln. part plays a similar eighth-note pattern. The Vc. part provides a steady bass line with quarter notes.

3^b Cl.

Vln.

Vc.

This system contains measures 13 through 19 of the piece. The 3^b Cl. part continues its melodic development. The Vln. part maintains its eighth-note texture. The Vc. part continues with a consistent quarter-note bass line. The system concludes with a double bar line.